

Fatty Acids of Fresh Water Fish Featherbacks

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Manuscript received 8 April 1976; revised 28 July 1976; accepted 2 August 1976

The fatty acid compositions of body, liver and visceral lipids of the two species of fresh water fish belonging to the family *Notoptoridae* namely Chital or humped-feather back, *Notopterus Chitala* (Ham) and pholui or feather-back, *Notopterus notopterus* (Pallus) have been determined by gas liquid chromatography (GLC). Major fatty acids found are 16:0, 16:1, 18:0, 18:1, 18:2 ω 6, 18:3 ω 3, 20:4 ω 6, 20:5 ω 3, 22:5 ω 3, 22:6 ω 3. High amounts (ca. 10-14%) of 20:4 ω 6 (arachidonic acid) unusual for fish, have been found to occur in liver lipids of both the species and body lipid of pholui.

FEATHERBACKS belonging to the family *Notoptoridae*, are tropical fishes that live in the weedy reaches of rivers, lakes and swamps. Out of the five species of featherbacks, only two are available in India and are extensively consumed. These are Chital or Humped-featherback, *Notopterus chitala* (Ham) and pholui or featherback, *Notopterus notopterus* (Pallus). The fatty acid compositions of the body, liver and visceral lipids of the above two species of featherbacks have been studied for the first time and reported in this paper.

Materials and Methods

The fishes were collected fresh and alive from the market during the end of September. Six fishes of each species were taken for analysis. Flesh, liver, and viscera were pooled separately, weighed and stored under nitrogen at -20° . Lipids were extracted out of these tissues following the procedure of Bligh and Dyer¹, dried under vacuo and weighed.

Saponification of the lipids, isolation of the resulting fatty acids and the preparation of the mixed methyl esters thereof, were done according to Metcalfe and Schmitz².

To check the presence of any unusual or conjugated polyunsaturated fatty acid, some of the methyl esters were subjected to thin layer chromatography on silica gel plate using a solvent mixture containing petroleum ether (40° - 60°), diethylether, acetic acid (80:20:1.5). Spectrophotometry of the mixed esters in the UV and IR regions were also done for the same purpose.

A portion of the methyl esters was catalytically hydrogenated³ at room temperature using Pt-catalyst. The methyl esters and their hydrogenated products were analysed by GLC.

An F & M Model 700-R dual column analytical gas chromatography with dual flame ionization detector was used. Chromatograms were taken on two stainless steel columns 6 ft. $\times$ 1/4 inch, packed respectively with 15% DEGS and 3% SE-30 coated

on 100-120 mesh gaschrom-P. The liquid phases and the solid support were procured from Applied Science Laboratories Inc., State College, Pennsylvania, U.S.A. The former was kept at 160° and the latter at 180° during operation. Nitrogen at a flow rate at 40 ml/min was used as carrier gas.

The GLC peaks were identified by (a) comparing the retention times with those of reference methyl esters, (b) determining the carbon number of the component esters before and after hydrogenation according to Ackman *et al.*⁴ using fatty acid methyl esters of Cod-liver oil as secondary standards.

Results and Discussion

Average weight and length of the fishes, lipid content per 100 g of the tissue, iodine value of the lipids and the methyl esters are presented in the

TABLE I

TABLE I—AVERAGE WEIGHT AND LENGTH, LIPID CONTENT, IODINE VALUES (WIJS') OF THE LIPID AND MIXED METHYL ESTERS OF FEATHERBACKS

	Chital	Pholui
Average weight (g)	4000	175
Average length (cm)	100	20
Lipid in body %	6	0.5
Lipid in liver %	2.3	0.5
Lipid in viscera %	20	0.6
Iodine value of body lipid	105	185
Iodine value of liver lipid	157	136
Iodine value of visceral lipid	85	104
Iodine value of mixed ME (body)	100	181
Iodine value of mixed ME (liver)	155	130
Iodine value of mixed ME (viscera)	82	102

Table 1. The two species differ widely regarding the distribution of lipids in the organs studied. In

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pholui the organs contain almost equal amount, ca. 0.5% of lipid. In chital, not only the lipid content in the organs are much higher than those in pholui, but also the distribution is not even. Viscera of chital contains as high as 20% lipid which is nearly 33 times more than that of pholui. In both the fishes the amount of unsaturation in the lipids differ from organ to organ as indicated by the iodine values of the lipids. This is highest in liver and lowest in visceral lipids. The close agreement between the experimental iodine values of the mixed methyl esters presented in this table with those calculated from the composition data (Table 2) serves as a good check on reliability of the latter

methylene interrupted polyunsaturated fatty acids normally present in animal lipids

Fatty acids compositions of the lipids computed from GLC of the mixed methyl esters are presented in Table 2. The compositions of the hydrogenated products of the mixed methyl esters are also incorporated in this table. The major fatty acids found were 16:0, 18:0, 18:1, 18:2 ω 6, 18:3 ω 3, 20:4 ω 6, 20:5 ω 3, 22:4 ω 6, 22:5 ω 3 and 22:6 ω 3. The saturated fatty acid content of all the lipids are in between 30 and 40% and is lowest in the body lipids of pholui. The levels of polyunsaturated fatty acids (dienic or hexaenoic) in the body, liver

TABLE 2—FATTY ACID COMPOSITIONS OF BODY, LIVER AND VISCERAL LIPID OF FEATHERBACKS (w/w%)

Components	Chital						Pholui					
	B		L		V		B		L		V	
	NH	H	NH	H	NH	H	NH	H	NH	H	NH	H
12:0	0.3	0.4	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
12:1	+		—		+		—		—		+	
14:0	5.1	4.9	1.1	1.3	1.3	1.3	0.7	2.0	2.0	2.2	2.7	2.5
14:1	+		+		+		+		+		+	
15:0	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	0.2	0.1
15:1	—		—		—		—		—		+	
16i	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
16:0	21.9	32.4	17.8	21.0	30.1	39.9	16.7	20.5	24.2	29.6	27.1	35.9
16:1	10.8		2.6		10.0		4.2		5.1		9.6	
17:0	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
17:1	+		+		+		—		—		—	
18i	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
18:0	18.2	46.0	21.9	43.8	8.9	49.2	13.5	38.3	18.4	40.6	14.3	40.9
18:1	21.4		15.0		30.8		21.4		17.1		19.9	
18:2 ω 6	2.7		3.7		6.7		3.3		2.6		4.3	
18:3 ω 3	2.5		2.1		3.4		0.9		1.9		2.3	
20:1												
18:4 ω 3	0.2		0.5		+		+		+		+	
20:0	+	8.4	+	19.4	+	5.6	+	15.0	+	17.1	+	10.9
20:2 ω 6	1.0		0.4		+		0.2		0.6		0.5	
20:3 ω 6	0.7		2.1		0.3		+		0.2		0.3	
20:4 ω 6	4.8		14.8		3.4		11.3		13.1		6.5	
22:1												
20:5 ω 3	2.2		2.7		1.6		3.1		4.0		1.5	
22:0	+	8.1	0.3	14.7	0.2	3.8	+	25.4	+	10.7	0.3	9.6
22:2 ω 6	0.5		+		+		+		+		+	
22:4 ω 6	0.8		2.2		+		2.1		2.2		3.2	
22:5 ω 6	0.5		1.7		+		1.5		1.2		0.4	
22:5 ω 3	2.9		1.4		1.2		2.2		2.2		1.4	
22:6 ω 3	3.7		9.4		1.9		18.8		5.1		4.3	
IV. calc. from comp.	99.7		153.1		80.0		182.3		129.9		103.0	

Thin layer chromatography on silica gel plate and spectral analysis both in IR and UV regions of the mixed methyl esters did not reveal the existence of any unusual or polyunsaturated fatty acids having unsaturation other than straight chain saturated and

and visceral lipids have been found to be respectively 22.8, 38.9 and 17.8% for chital and 42.7, 32.7 and 23.7% for pholui. The high levels of polyunsaturated fatty acids encountered in the lipids of these fishes is a feature common to all aquatic animals.

Lovern⁵ pointed out that in comparison to the fishes of marine origin the lipids of the fresh water ones are richer in C₁₆ and C₁₈ acids with corresponding lower levels of C₂₀ and C₂₂ acids. This generalization has been confirmed by recent studies on fresh water species of subtropical water^{6,7}. The present results of featherbacks follow in general the above pattern. The presence of high amounts ca. 10 to 14% of arachidonic acid (20 : 4 ω 6) in the liver lipids of both the species and body lipids of pholui is noteworthy, as the level of this acid is in general much lower in animal lipids. Only comparable amounts have been very recently found to occur in the lipids of murrelets⁷, another family of fresh water fishes and in one species of shark⁸. It is known that monoenoic acids of fish lipids contain various isomeric acids with different ω values^{9,10} which could be separated only by the use of high efficiency open tubular columns. In the present study such separation were not possible with the packed column used and it is probable that different isomeric monoenoic acids may be present in the lipids studied.

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